

Research

The Malian Crisis of 2012: Key Players to Better Understand the Crisis

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Abstract: The crisis in Mali emerged from a combination of internal rebellion and state breakdown, along with external attacks, posing a significant threat to the country's unity, territorial integrity, and democratic traditions. The immediate cause of the crisis was the Tuareg revolt, driven by longstanding tensions with the Malian government, with the Tuaregs seeking autonomy in the Azawad region.

Keywords: Malian army, MNLA, ECOWAS, France.

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Introduction

This paper will explore the key actors and their specific interests in the background of the crisis. This includes both the internal as well as external actors.

Mali is going through a profound problem which has significant political, socio-economic and humanitarian outcomes as well as those of defense and human freedoms. The challenges are the state's federal unity, its territorial integrity, and its multi-ethnic and secular democratic tradition. The recent war in northern Mali is grounded primarily and only in its particular national and regional context. Regional growths are just one factor of this problem. But the regional context of the war in Mali has been widely misinterpreted, or at least misnamed, as existing Sahel specific.

The conflicts in Mali began in March 2012 when the Northern-based Tuareg revolutionist organization bombarded towns in Northern Mali, pursuing the fluctuation engineered by an overthrow of Amadou Toure regime. The rebel assaulted the main cities in the Northern part of Mali and continued to live in some key territories. From 2012 to the present day, the crisis has left thousands of dead on the side of Malian and jihadist soldiers, foreign forces but also on the side of the civilian population.

The Malian crisis of 2012 was a combination of internal rebellion and breakdown of state structures, on the one hand, and of external attacks, which collectively jeopardized the integrity of the state.

The immediate cause was the revolt of the Tuareg, who live in Kidal, in the Northern region of Mali. Their tensions with the Malian government have a long-standing history. From the beginning of Mali's independence, the Tuareg of the North started a series of attacks against the government in 1960 to 1963, 1988 to 1996, 2006 to 2008, and 2012, and

fighting continues. The Tuaregs are ethnically different from the population in Southern Mali. While they live in five Sahel states, only the Tuaregs of Mali have had a secessionist strategy with a center in Azawad, their place of origin. Now, several live in what they consider the Azawad region which stretches across northern Mali from Mali which borders Niger, Algeria, and Libya. The north of Mali comprises two-thirds of the area of the country, but only a ten percent of the population live there, of whom the majority are Tuaregs. They have organized in a Movement for the Liberation of Azawad (MNLA after its French name, *Mouvement national de libération de l'Azawad*). In early 2012, the MNLA made an attempt to overthrow authorities in northern Mali.

Who are actors of the crisis, who they are, and what their interests are?

Internal actors:

The Malian army (state actor, non-Islamist; founded in 1960) :

The Malian army is defined as being a hierarchy under pressure, defined not only by an absence of skills, an imbalance between officers and conscripted soldiers but also by an inequality provoked by the injection of financial assistance from the Western powers, which supported a safety strategy by investing in the army rather than in development assistance.

In November 2011, the Malian troops were attacked by Tuareg combatants in many areas and the cities of the north (Tinzawaten, Tessalit). Many Malian fighters were captured or murdered in Aguel'hoc, which the military was forced to abandon. Attempting to keep this series of setbacks, the regime clarified that it had opted for a "strategic retreat" from the region. The defeat of the Malian troop pursuing the MNLA offensive, and in particular the killing of Malian combatants in Aguelhok, in the northeast in 2012, led to an immediate worsening of the crisis, but in the southern part of Mali, and in particular in the capital, Bamako.

In March 20 several women and children of combatants had journeyed from the battalion city of Koulouba to the presidential villa in Bamako. They were boycotting administration privacy shrouding a fatal assault on the Malian troop by Tuareg revolutionist in Alguelhok in the north. Husbands, mums, and sisters all required to understand how many fighters had perished and whether their household members had survived. The following day Combatants from the Kati battalion, at the entrances of Bamako, are heading towards the presidency, on Koulouba ridge, to complain against the absence of means at their disposal to respond. In Thursday 22, 2012, a few weeks before the presidential election, which would end President Touré's term, the military acting under the name of the National Committee for the Recovery of Democracy and the Restoration of the State dissolved all institutions and suspended the constitution. Captain Amadou Sanogo overthrew former President ATT, creating the National Committee for the Recovery of Democracy and the State (CNDR).

The main reason for their revolts was the massacre of Malian soldiers in the north of Mali, and wanted a reaction from the government to this situation, and also that the government provide them with the necessary means to the army so that they can face the rebels because many soldiers complain of not having the necessary means to face the rebels. Apart from that, the country had many problems such as problems in education, teachers were on strike claiming several months of unpaid salaries, irregularities in the field of public service, and unemployment was increasing almost no recruitment, all these problems according to Amadou Sanogo have weighed in the decision of the putsch. He declared in the name of the CNRDRE that he wanted good training for the Malian army, better living conditions for the military throughout Mali, and to rebuild not only the army but also Mali as a whole.

Movement for the Liberation of Azawad (MNLA)

The Movement for the Liberation of Azawad (MNLA) emerged in October 2011. The MNLA was the latest in a succession of associations involved in Tuareg revolts that happened and reoccurred over the 50 years since Malian sovereignty.

The Tuaregs have had tensions against the authorities in place, tensions against the French during colonization and after decolonization against the central authority of the Malian state. The Tuaregs, before Mali's independence, made known to France their desire not to be attached to any state. But their request was not taken into account by France, and this explains in a logical way between 1962 and 1964, the Tuaregs rebelled against the new Malian authorities in place in the north of Mali in the region of Kidal who wanted their organization. The crisis of 2012 is a new uprising of the Tuaregs in the North, just like the last one in 2008, whose goal is to take their autonomy within Mali, that is, independence with the creation of a new state, the of a new state, Azawad.

The Tuaregs are part of the minority ethnic groups of Mali, they represent only 5 to 6%, and they are essentially based in the north of the country, more precisely in Kidal. His request is simple: the sovereignty of Azawad, an area of 800,000 km² in the north of Mali including the areas of Timbuktu, Kidal, and Gao), or more than half of Mali. After the entrance of Tuaregs trained in the Libyan army or militias and weapons from Libya, the MNLA undertaken to dominate northern Mali in January 2012, but it rapidly overwhelmed by Islamist movements that expel him from cities (Gao, Timbuktu, Kidal...) in June / July.

After the MNLA attacked the Malian government, they were joined by other Salafist groups whose objectives were not the same. The MNLA had to collaborate with them with the objective of fighting the Malian army in the north in order to recover the north. A division within the MNLA was noticeable as some agents asserted that the MNLA was a non-religious activity pursuing sovereignty for the secular nation of Azawad, but others named for the achievement of an Islamic republic. The MNLA in May 2012 was forced to leave the territories it controlled, and more specifically its major urban centers (Gao, Kidal and Timbuktu) to armed Islamist organizations. The latter have collaboration with Al Qaeda and are classified as Salafi jihadist groups given their objectives and ideology.

Salafi-jihadist movements:

The first one is AQIM (Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb) is an offshoot of the Algerian civil war of the 1990s. It is a transformation of the GSPC (Salafist Group of Preaching and Jihad), which was founded by Hassan Hattab in 1998, commander of the GIA (Armed Islamic Groups) in Kabylia, whose aim was the fight against the policy of indiscriminate massacres of civilians. AQIM is a terrorist organization that can easily adapt to the region in which it operates, and it has a history of resisting counterterrorism operations. AQIM is focused entirely on Algeria and neighbouring countries. AQIM elements claim to be part of the jihadist tendency of the Salafism. They are trying to establish the authentic caliphate through jihad, which they consider as an absolute obligation. They have tried to take control of the Sahara-Sahelian zone to create the basis of their mission to reconquer the umma (community) Muslim. Limited in 2010 AQIM's workforce has risen considerably thanks in particular to important financial resources from ransoms paid by some nations for the delivery of their prisoners and several trafficking in which they are involved (drugs, cigarettes, migrants...). The jihadist group has labored in Western hostage-taking, with ransoms characterizing the majority of its resources, along with drug trafficking. A recent exchange in human beings has developed: Mafia systems kidnap and sell their prisoners to AQIM, who also come into negotiations with the state of origin. Organized mainly by Mauritians and Malians but led by Algerians, the movement is said to be made up of a thousand men deployed in the phalanges of the Sahara grouped in northern Mali. Placed since January 2012 in Timbuktu, which has become its central defense, AQIM's major partner in northern Mali is the Islamist group Ansar Dine, led by a Malian, Iyad Ag Ghaly. By pure policy, the jihadists do not have substantial security devices in the central towns of northern Mali.

The fact that other ethnic rebel groups exist such as MUJAO and Ansar Dine has been an opportunity for AQIM to implement its philosophy, which is nothing more than to separate jihadists into racially and ethnically distinct organizations while maintaining the supremacy of AQIM and its Arab leaders in the jihadi leadership.

The second one is Ansar Dine, in 2012, when the crisis in northern Mali began, the armed Salafi-jihadist organization Ansar Dine quickly became one of its main protagonists. Below this name which indicates "Defenders of Islam" in Arabic,

this direction that supports extreme Islam officially joined the event in November 2011. The Ansar Dine group emerged in early 2012. Ansar Dine differs from other groups in its composition and territorial claims. Ansar Dine is overwhelmingly Malian; it is also composed of ex-rebels Tuaregs, some of whom initiated the clash against the state Malian for over 20 years and, in its early years, did not pursue a transnational Islamist agenda. This is especially the example for their commander; Iyad ag Ghali began the Tuareg revolt on June 28, 1990.

Established by Iyad Ag Ghaly, Ansar Dine establishes himself the purpose of assigning Sharia law across the state and making Mali a theocracy. Ag Ghali is one of the oldest Tuareg leaders in the region. Since 1990, he has been involved in the political and military affairs of northern Mali, and in particular in the same year he joined a Tuareg rebellion and subsequently signed a treaty with the central government. He created Ansar al-Din because the MNLA refused to integrate him because of the role he played in previous rebellions. Following this, Ag Ghali founded his own group and initially cooperated with the MNLA.

In mid-January 2012, Ansar Dine took command of a huge area in the north of the country, owning the cities of Tinzouaten, Tessalit, and Aguelhok, close to the Algerian frontier. With the assistance of distinct elements of AQIM and the MLNA, the movement took control of the cities of Kidal, Gao, and Timbuktu in the days that attended and assessed Sharia law there. In June 2012, Ansar Dine demolished many mausoleums of Muslim saints in Timbuktu, in reprisal for Unesco's ruling to classify the city as "World Heritage in Danger". The members of AQIM claim to be part of the jihadist trend of salafism. They want to rebuild the original caliphate (a territory of the Muslim population) through jihad, which they consider an absolute obligation. They are trying to make the Sahara-Sahel area the basis of their project to reconquer the Muslim ummah (community).

The third one is the MUJAO, emerging from a split from AQIM in the summer of 2011, was established in the purpose to expand the Islamist revolution from the Maghreb to Africa from the West is based on local people. It looks like although the Islamist philosophy is only a mask for actions generally mafia (kidnappings, trafficking of all kinds, generally drugs). The movement, which has a single objective, which is to extend the jihadist insurgency throughout West Africa, had just split with Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM). Unlike AQIM, the majority of MUJAO members are Malians, active in the Gao region. The MUJAO is led by the Mauritanian Hamada Ould Mohamed Kheirou.

With crucial armed reserves, the Mujao is captivating more and more sub-Saharan jihadist apprentices, little persuaded by Aqmi. The Mujao later became one of the masters of northern Mali. After the MNLA attack in January 2012 in northern Mali, with AQIM as a partner, Mujao became a major player alongside Al-Qaeda and Ansar Eddine. Mujao has taken control of the main towns in the region, making Gao its stronghold by June 2012. After clashes with the MNLA, which subsequently left the city, Mujao became the absolute master of the city.

External actors

2.1 Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS):

Established in 1975, ECOWAS is a West African intergovernmental organization and the main structure for coordinating the actions and policies of West African countries. Its objective is to facilitate cooperation and integration in order to create a West African economic and monetary union. ECOWAS has 15 West African countries as members such as: Mali, Mauritania, Benin, Senegal etc... For Mali, as for other West African countries, ECOWAS is an organization that serves as a platform to assert their national and regional interests and influences. ECOWAS is one of the most developed sub-regional organizations in the field of peace operations. In the aftermath of the military coup of March 2012, ECOWAS, like the Western governments, condemned this violation of republican legality.

In March 2012 ECOWAS assembled a Tremendous Conference of Regional Leaders in the Ivory Coast to discuss ways to secure an immediate recovery to Mali fundamental law, also discuss about the regulations to maintain and defend Mali territorial integrity on. In Mali ECOWAS arbitrage followed an extended approach by trying to find common

ground with the military, who had staged the coup, to resolve the political crisis, and to find a solution quickly to stop the violence in the North. The mediation strategy was directed towards the actors of the military coup because they controlled Mali at the period, to rapidly establish a transitional administration to govern the country.

ECOWAS has placed an embargo on Mali, closing the borders of Mali's neighboring countries, but also the neighboring seaports to all trade, a very difficult sanction for the Malian government insofar as Mali is highly dependent on foreign trade with its neighbors. This ECOWAS sanction was intended to put pressure on the military to hand over power to a civilian in order to Mali's return to constitutional order. On April 6, the junta and ECOWAS reached an agreement in which the junta agreed to hand over power to a civilian to restore constitutional order in exchange for amnesty for junta members and the lifting of sanctions.

2.2 France as a colonizing country:

At the beginning of January 2013, in this period all the attempts for a solution did not succeed, because in 2012 the EU took the decision not to send a military mission, the UN also was not going to send soldiers and the African Presidents were thinking about the modalities of deployment of an African force. Also, those in charge of advising President François Hollande on Africa were not saying anything and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs was following the developments in Africa closely, but was much more focused on the situation in Syria. Following this, the chief of staff, General Puga, who informed Hollande that soldiers were ready to intervene in Mali.

A few days after, Hollande declared the launch of Operation Serval. 4,000 French soldiers have been mobilized for the military operation in northern Mali. The French military presence must take into account the deployment of the African-led International Support Mission in Mali under African leadership (MISMA), pending the deployment of a UN force. It is clear that Operation Serval is a new response to new challenges, both in terms of objectives and strategy and tactics. It is not in line with the traditional interventions of the French army in Africa. After a few months, President Hollande ended Operation Serval and launched Operation Barkhane in northern Mali. The Serval operation was for a short period, but Barkhane is for a long period. Because France, together with local and global partners have defined the danger as a terrorist danger, which led to the creation of the Barkhane operation, which will involve many military commands around the Sahel.

The French intervention has received mixed reviews with some condemning the country for its perceived double standards that seek to promote its interests: insofar as Mali has a politico-military dependence on the French state a French monopoly of raw materials, economic and monetary links, in the Malian conflict whilst simultaneously pursuing a humanitarian stance. Also for the French, this conflict in northern Mali is a great danger for the entire Sahel region and if the rebels were to take control of Mali it could destabilize Mali's neighbouring states, including Niger, Algeria and Mauritania. These states maintain economic relations with France. The major critique of the French intervention was that the real reason was to protect France's financial interests in northern Mali but more precisely in the Sahara region. In specific, developed where the uranium mines in Niger, supervised by AREVA, or the often unexploited natural resources in Mali or other nations of the Sahel. One of France's main sources of electricity is nuclear power, and 1/3 of France's uranium mines are based in northern Niger. Consequently, the Niger mine is located in the town of Arlit, about 200 miles from the Malian border. France feared that rebel forces would attack the mine and take hostages.

Conclusion

The crisis in Mali is a perfect example of the weakness of states that cannot secure their entire territory following an independence insurrection or terrorist attack. The complexity of the alliances between the different rebel groups and their changing objectives partly explain the difficulty in finding a political solution to the crisis. Those differences make it extremely difficult to agree on common discussion points and any viable solution to the crisis continues to be unattainable. Not all Salafist groups have the same vision, but AQIM and Ansar Al-Din share almost the same vision, as

AQIM and Ansar Al-Din have adopted the same religious ideals. Despite these religious ideals, there is a difference between the two groups. This difference lies in the scope of the struggle in which the two groups want to engage; building an Islamic state according to Salafist rules in Mali, without conflict with the West, is the goal of Ansar Al-Din, while AQIM has a global vision, that of Al-Qaeda.

The reason the diplomatic community took up the Malian crisis is that there were concerns about the deteriorating security situation and the displacement of alleged terrorist-affiliated groups to the south. The case of northern Mali also proves that with the new challenges that the international community is facing seems to be in difficulty, insofar as it is France that has intervened to put order in Mali, but also with the assistance of ECOWAS.

France is pursuing its interest (economic, terrorism) not only in Mali, but also in the Sahel region. Because France in terms of natural resources has a strong dependence on Mali with gold and Niger with uranium, and on the Sahel side it has been several years that France is engaged in the fight against terrorism and the Malian crisis has further strengthened this fight. These reasons explain the reason and the interest of the French intervention in Mali. The interest of ECOWAS in the Malian crisis is to find a common ground between the Malian government, the Toureges and the Salafi-djihadist movements to put an end to this crisis, which may affect other ECOWAS member countries whose interest is to end the conflict as soon as possible.

The external actors have in common the will to stabilize northern Mali by trying to find a point of contact between the Malian state, the Tuaregs, and the Salafi-jihadist movements, but also in reorganizing the state. Insofar as this Malian crisis is a risk for the entire sub-region, more precisely for West Africa and the Sahel region.

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